

Anonymous players soccer 2d simulation team description 2024

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Abstract. Soccer simulation 2D is a computerized version of a real soccer game in two dimensions, where two teams of 11 players and one coach compete against each other using artificial intelligence and robotics techniques. One of the challenges in this field is to predict the passing behavior of the players, which is crucial for keeping the ball possession and creating scoring opportunities. Different methods and features have been proposed to address this problem using deep neural networks, random forest, reinforcement learning, and Monte Carlo tree search. The performance of these methods is evaluated against the top teams of RoboCup, an international competition for promoting research in A.I. and robotics. Soccer simulation 2D has various applications for real soccer and other domains.

Keywords: RoboCup, 2D Simulated

1 Introduction

The RoboCup 2D Simulated Soccer League is a computer-based competition where software agents play soccer in a virtual 2D environment. It is the oldest and most established league in the RoboCup Soccer Simulation domain, which aims to foster research and education in artificial intelligence and robotics.

Unlike other leagues that involve physical robots, the 2D Simulation League does not require any hardware or sensors. Instead, the matches are displayed on a large screen, resembling a video game. Each team consists of 11 software agents, each with its own strategy and behavior. The agents communicate with a central server, called Soccer-Server, which simulates the physics and dynamics of the game. The server also provides noisy and relative sensory information to the agents, such as vision, sound, and touch. The agents can perform basic actions, such as dashing, turning, or kicking, to influence the game state. The main challenge in the 2D Simulation League is to develop intelligent and cooperative agents that can cope with uncertainty and complexity. The agents have to infer the best possible action from their sensory input, which is often incomplete and inaccurate. They also have to coordinate with their teammates and adapt to their

opponents. The agents have to make these decisions within 100 ms, which is the length of each game cycle. A typical game lasts for 6000 cycles, or 10 minutes. **Sample Heading (Third Level)**. Only two levels of headings should be numbered. Lower level headings remain unnumbered; they are formatted as run-in headings^{[1][2][10]}

1.1 Related Work

Here is a summary of the main contributions of the articles from other 2D teams that inspired our work.

Team HELIOS2022 is a successful RoboCup team that has been competing since 2000. The team's recent research is about how the team name affects the game outcome in the soccer simulation league.^{[5][9]}

Cyrus Team is a successful soccer simulation team that has participated in various RoboCup and IranOpen events since 2013. The team is based on agent2d.^{[4][7][8]}

Perspolis is a student team that aims to participate in World Cup competitions. The team has won third place in IranOpen2017 and IranOpen2018. The team uses artificial intelligence for decision making and online analysis.^[3]

Next, we will examine the modifications made in this article.

2 Pass

Pass part is a function that tries to pass the ball to a teammate in a soccer simulation game. The game is a simplified version of real soccer, where two teams of eleven players each try to score goals by kicking the ball into the opponent's net. The game is divided into two halves of 45 minutes each, and the team with the most goals at the end wins.

The code takes an agent as a parameter, which represents the player who has the ball. The agent has attributes such as position, velocity, direction, stamina, and skills, which affect its performance in the game. The agent also has access to the world model, which is a data structure that contains information about the game state, such as the positions of the ball and the players, the score, the time, and the game mode.

The code uses the world model to get information about the game state, such as the positions of the ball and the players. It finds the possible teammates to pass the ball to by creating a sector around each teammate and checking if there is no opponent in the sector. A sector is a triangular area that extends from the agent to the teammate, with a certain angle and radius. The angle and radius depend on the agent's skills and the game mode. For example, a skilled agent can create a larger sector than a less skilled one, and a defensive game mode requires a smaller sector than an offensive one.

3 Shoot

The function is called shoot, and it tries to make the player who has the ball kick it towards the goal. The function takes one input, which is the player who has the ball. The function gives one output, which is either true or false. The output is true if the kick was successful and the ball went into the goal. The output is false if the kick was not successful and the ball missed the goal or was blocked by another player.

The function works by using the world model, which is a representation of the game state that includes the positions and velocities of the ball and the players, as well as other information such as the game mode, the score, and the time. The function uses the world model to get the position of the ball and the goal posts. The goal posts are the two vertical poles that mark the boundaries of the goal. The function then finds the best goal post to kick towards by measuring the distances from the ball. The best goal post is the one that is closer to the ball and has a larger angle from the center of the goal. The function then calculates the power of the kick based on the game mode, which is a variable that indicates the level of difficulty or the type of scenario of the game. The function then uses a smart kick method to execute the kick action. The smart kick method is a technique that I developed to make the kick more accurate and effective. The smart kick method considers the direction, the speed, and the spin of the ball, as well as the position and the movement of the other players, to adjust the kick parameters. The function then returns the output, which is true or false depending on the result of the kick.

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